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Cognomentisation: A Jungian Archetype and Typology of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Yoruba Creativity

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Abstract

Cognomentisation is a cultural practice of assigning or ascribing a cognomen to an individual. The **cognomen** itself is that name or designation which mirrors typical attributes of the person, or their lineage. In antiquity, it was Roman to have a cognomen, the third name of a citizen which is usually passed down their generations. This in later years became a derivative from an ancestor's sobriquet or distinctive feature. *Orúko Oríkì* in the Yoruba culture is a type of cognomen given at birth. It usually a single praise name attached to an irregular ode (non-Pandoric, non-Horatian) chanted poetically; connecting the child to their local collective unconscious as Yoruba. The 'mothers' are typical griots in this instance. They begin by calling the *Orúko Oríkì* and advance into chanting the orature associated with the *Orúko Oríkì*. This they do fondly whenever the child greets in the morning, or when he has done something prodigious. The performance of *Oríkì*, being chanted gets the child feeling electrified, inspired, got 'swollen headed', or excited. By transliteration, the word *Oríkì* = *Orí* (the head) + *kíkì* (accolade), essentially describing the invocation of the vigour of the head which the culture perceives as the greatest *Òrìṣà*. The reflective argument in this paper is the cognitive arousal the individual experiences when his *Oríkì* is being chanted, and the creativity of the griot. This performance by implication links the child with their ancestral past in the Jungian collective unconscious; and simultaneously propels them into a creative future of which AI is a type. Carl Jung described the collective unconscious as the deeper, ancestral, unlearned, shared aspects of the psyche that transcend personal experience, and psychological inheritance common to all human. This study encourages the oral performance of the *Oríkì* through AI for optimal human functioning, especially as the generation of the human griots declines.

Keyword: Cognomen, Culture Creativity, Yoruba, Artificial Intelligence, Oríkì, Collective Unconscious, Local Collective Unconscious

Introduction

The term "cognomentisation" is not a popular or frequently used word in the academia or everyday speech. It is a word that grew with the history of ancient Rome. Historically, a cognomen was the third name in Roman naming conventions. A male Roman citizen in the late Republic and early Empire usually had three names known as the *tria nomina*. *This comprise of:* Praenomen (the given name or personal name, used to distinguish an individual within their family. Examples include Marcus, Gaius, or Lucius). Nomen (the family or clan name (gens) which indicating the broader family group to which an individual belonged. Examples include Julius (from the gens Julia) or Cornelius (from the gens Cornelia)). Cognomen (Originally a nickname or descriptor, it later became a hereditary surname within a family. It often referred to physical traits, accomplishments, or other characteristics. Examples include: Cicero (meaning "chickpea") or Caesar (possibly meaning "hairy" or "cut by caesarean") (Nuorluoto, 2021). It is intriguing to realise Merriam-Webster describing a 'cognomen as "a descriptive or familiar name given instead of or in addition to the one belonging to an individual" (Merriam-Webster, n.d.). The Britannica also described cognomen as 'a hereditary name' (Zgusta, 2024). In essence, the '**-isation**' is a suffix depicting "the process of creating the cognomen which some authorities describe as 'surname'. For all intents and purposes, "cognomentisation" could be interpreted as the process of assigning or creating a name, title, or identifier – perhaps one that carries specific meanings or connotations. In the context of AI, this concept might relate to how AI systems generate, assign, or understand names and identifiers, particularly in the context of natural language processing (NLP), machine learning, or identity creation; more importantly, considering the AI generating newer customised cognomen (*Oríkì*) for the new generation (Yadav, Patel, & Shah, M., 2021; Vajjala, Majumder, Gupta, & Surana, 2020).

"Oríkì" is a significant cultural and linguistic concept in Yoruba culture, functioning as more than just praise poetry or a recitation of a lineage. By transliteration, the word *Oríkì* = *Orí* (the head) + *kíkì* (accolade). By

implication, the *Oríkì* is about invoking the vigour of the head. In Yorùbáland, there are various types of *Oríkì*. As Tunji Vidal puts it the Yoruba people are so rich in the use of *Oríkì* such that they even have *Oríkì* for the foods they eat (Vidal, 1969). Hence, there are *Oríkì* for towns known as *Oríkì Ìlú* as in, *Oríkì Ìbàdàn*, *È`gbá*, *Ìjèsà*, *Ìgbètì*, *Ìwó*, *Şakí*, etc.; *Oríkì Òrìşà* (Deity *Oríkì*); *Oríkì Oníşé* (Profession-Based *Oríkì*); *Oríkì Àwọ̀n Èranko* (Animal *Oríkì*); *Orúko Oríkì* (cognomen, or personal praise name) etc.

For the purpose of the work, instead of the general forms of *Oríkì*, we shall be considering *Orúko Oríkì*, although in the course of the work both *Orúko Oríkì* and *Oríkì* would be used interchangeably to mean same referent. *Orúko Oríkì* in the Yoruba culture is a cognomen given at birth. It is usually a single praise name such as: *Àjàní*, *Àmọ̀ kẹ́*, *Àlámú*, *Àdùnní*. These cognomens or *Orúko Oríkì* are attached to an irregular ode (non-Pandoric, non-Horatian) chanted poetically; and thus connecting the child to their local collective unconscious. The ‘mothers’ are typical griots in this instance. They begin by calling the *Orúko Oríkì* and then advance into chanting the orature associated with the *Orúko Oríkì*. This they do fondly whenever the child greets in the morning, or when he has done something prodigious. Here below is a short extract of the *Orúko Oríkì* of a male called *Àjàní È`dú*:

Èmi Àjàní È`dú
Ọmọ olólà
Ọmọ ológun àsabàrí
Àganran ilé, àganran oko.
T'óbá d'ọjọ́ aré, eránni sí ológun
T'óbá d'ọjọ́ `jà, eránni sí Àsabàrí.
Ọmọ òkè túrú nínú igbó Asabari.

Èmi lọ mọ òkè òjẹ, òkè ò mú.
Ọmọ òkè tú rú rú nínú igbó Àsabàrí
Ọmọ igbó ruru níwájú ológun.
Ológun òní k'aré, Àsabàrí òní k'ọ `jà
Òní ùwọ ọkọ baba mí òò
Ìgbà t'ó mọ `pé kí o mé è dẹ `gàn
Emi lopé n wá nú ọkọ şe...

Jungian Collective Unconscious and *Oríkì*

Carl Jung, a Swiss psychiatrist and psychoanalyst, introduced the concept of the Collective Unconscious as a key part of his analytical psychology. The Collective Unconscious refers to structures of the unconscious mind shared among beings of the same species. It is different from the personal unconscious, which contains an individual's repressed memories, desires, and experiences (Jung, 1959). The collective unconscious is populated by archetypes, which are universal, primal symbols and themes that recur across different cultures and time periods. Archetypes can be understood as inherited potentials that shape human perception and behaviour. Some well-known archetypes and concepts discussed below.

i. The Self

According to Jung, the self represents the central archetype and the totality of the psyche which integrates both the ego (the centre of consciousness and the unconscious layers of the individual (i.e. both personal unconscious and collective unconscious) (Jung, 2014). It is a symbol of unity, wholeness, and the process of putting together all parts of the psyche: light and shadow, conscious and unconscious, masculine and feminine into a balanced and harmonious whole to achieve inner balance and authenticity (Hills, 2001). The Self is not just a theoretical concept but a dynamic goal – the ultimate expression of individuality and interconnectedness with the greater whole of humanity and the universe (Meier, 2023).

ii. The Shadow

The Jungian shadow is a part of the personality that resides in the unconscious. It embodies the darker, often repressed, aspects of every man. The shadow refers to that aspect of an individual which one does not recognise or accept as part of one self; including undesirable traits or emotions one finds incompatible with one's self-image, or public image such as greed, or anger (Gorban, 2013). The Shadow often contains inhibited desires, instincts, weaknesses, and fears that can influence thoughts, behaviours, and emotions if left unexamined. The shadow can be negatively creative. This is observed sometimes, when a social deviant behaviour is expressed in acts such as arson, or homicide, the society marvels at such a negatively impacting negativity. There are

also times, we project the traits of our shadow onto others, judging them for qualities we dislike, or deny in ourselves. For instance, disliking someone for being arrogant might stem from suppressed arrogance within you. The *Oríkì* makes this reality apparent in the process of chanting. But it then the responsibility of the bearer to accept this dark side of his existence and engage an opportunity for personal growth by addressing this aspect of his life for better productivity.

iii. **The Anima and Animus**

The concept of the anima and animus are described as an abstract part of the self in the unconscious as found in the Jungian tradition. They represent the assertion of the presence of an opposite gender archetype in every human. By implication, that a feminine archetype resides within men (anima) and that a masculine archetype exists within the womenfolk (animus). These archetypal components of the collective unconscious represent the opposite gender within each individual (Cooper, 2020). They serve as bridges between the conscious and unconscious in the psyche, playing a crucial role in psychological development and self-discovery (Loftin, M. (2010). The anima (feminine component in a man) connects him to his inner world of emotions, creativity, intuition, and nurturing qualities (Hill, 1998). The animus on the other hand is the masculinity in a woman which links her to capacities such as logic, assertiveness, and her capacity for action and rational thought, shaped by her experience with male figures such as fathers, brothers, or mentors (Galli Carminati, Carminati & Demongeot, 2024).

iv. **The Ego**

The ego is another archetype and the very centre of consciousness. The ego is different from the self; while ego is primarily conscious the self is both conscious and unconscious. The ego organises the human conscious thoughts, perceptions, memories and experiences he is aware of; as well as acts as a bridge between the external world and the internal psyche (Burnett, 2023). The ego offers man the sense of consciousness, continuity and selfhood, maintaining that awareness of "I" or "me." This is exactly the object of the concept of *Oríkì*. When the griot raises her voice, it is the ego that is being addressed. In the Jungian tradition, the psyche is a combination of the ego (though a small component of the

psyche, but governs the human conscious functioning), personal unconscious (the container of forgotten or repressed memories unique to the individual) and the collective unconscious (the reservoir of universal symbols and archetypes shared across humanity).

v. **The Child in the Jungian Tradition**

The Child in the Jungian theory is that archetype which embodies purity, creativity, curiosity, rebirth, renewal, future growth and a fresh perspective (Jung, 1996). That is your inner child that aspires to be great, prosperous, and responsible. This is that very component that swells your head when your *Oriki* is being chanted (Taofeek & Oyeyemi, 2022; Bangura, 2015). It is that part of us that marvels at the world and remains open us to new experiences. It symbolises the beginning of development and the promise of what we might become. The Child carries the seeds of the future within, representing untapped potential. This archetype also acknowledges our early experiences of dependence and need for care, often tied to our formative relationships with caregivers (Knox, 2001). The Child often appears in myths and stories as a symbol of transformation and new beginnings, suggesting that returning to a childlike state of openness can lead to personal renewal and immutable growth (Bassil-Morozow, 2023). Working with the Child archetype in therapy or self-reflection can help individuals reconnect with their inner child, heal past wounds, and rediscover a sense of joy (McGurn, 1998).

vi. **Universal Experience**

According to Carl Jung, the Collective Unconscious connects all humans, providing a shared foundation of experience and understanding that transcends individual differences (Jung, 1936). This is the essence of humanity. Key components of the universal experience are: the collective unconscious, archetypes, myths and symbols and synchronicity. That is why this experience is said to be universal. In his works, he explained that everyone is born with this archetype and the collective unconscious; hence, these are not acquired by way of individual experiences, but owe their existence to a form of genetics (Jung, 1936; 2014; Stevens, 2012; Hauke, 2012). Like the instincts we observe in animals, these are a part of our psychological heritage. Essentially, Jung's ideas emphasise that beneath cultural and individual

differences lies a shared human essence. This universality has been influential in psychology, literature, and the arts, encouraging a deeper understanding of the interconnectedness of human experience.

vii. Local Experience

The concept of a "local collective unconscious" is not directly Jungian but that of the authors who are of the opinion that if there is a universal unconscious, there should be a local version. This is perceptibly intriguing as one view it through the lens of cultural psychology and social dynamics. While Carl Jung originally proposed the **collective unconscious** as a universal psychological structure shared by all humans, shaped by archetypes and ancestral experiences, a localised version emerges in specific contexts. For instance, Communities often share myths, stories, traditions, and rituals unique to their region, shaping a collective mental framework. In the Yoruba parlance we have the myth of the orisas: Obatala, Sango, Esu, etc. These legends, their stories and traditions behind them as well as the rituals involved in their veneration are unique to the Yoruba localisation. Same goes for environmental experience of a fishing community like the Ilajes (a Yoruba sub-group) may develop shared instincts and unconscious values around water, tides, and community interdependence, distinct from mountain-dwelling communities in Oke-Ogun (a town in the southwest of Nigeria). The local collective unconscious can also take the form of shared history: of migrations, inter and intra-ethnic wars, or colonisation which create a unique psychological imprint. These events often manifest in collective memory, trauma, or resilience patterns that resonate within the subconscious of a localised group.

viii. Cultural and Mythological Expressions

The theory of collective unconscious is expressed through myths, dreams, religious rituals, and cultural symbols. Jung's theory states that human experiences are genetically coded and passed down through generations. In practice, cultural and mythological expressions are explored through:

- a) **Dreams and Myths** – dreams are visions we see when we sleep while myths are incredible stories of animate and inanimate objects we have been told in our culture, or elsewhere. Jung believed that dreams often carry mythological motifs, reflecting

personal struggles or universal truths. For example, the appearance of a masquerade chasing a person in a dream may symbolise an archetypal battle with the unconscious Shadow of that personality.

- b) **Cross-Cultural Parallels** – Jung explored similarities between myths across cultures, such as flood myths or hero archetypes, to demonstrate the universality of archetypal patterns. There is hardly a culture without a myth. Myths relating to flood or heroes are myths he found to be universal, hence drawing a similarity between cultures no matter how sophisticated or remote; and alluding that all men have a common universal experience.
- c) **Art and Rituals** – Artistic expressions and rituals are seen as ways to externalise and connect with archetypes. For example, religious ceremonies often evoke archetypal imagery like death and rebirth, mirroring psychological transformation. Hence, mythological motifs and cultural symbols emerge from this collective layer, offering a universal language of the psyche. These expressions are universal, showing up in different forms across various cultures, yet they carry similar meanings and themes because they stem from the same archetypal structures (Jung, 1969; Jung & von Franz, 1964).

ix. **Psychological Influence**

The collective unconscious influences individual behaviour, thoughts, and emotions, often without the person being consciously aware of it. Understanding and integrating these unconscious elements into conscious awareness is a central goal in Jungian therapy, helping individuals achieve psychological balance and self-realisation (Gordon, 2023). A lot of the times there are imbalances. Imbalances, such as over-identification with the Persona or suppression of the Shadow, can lead to psychological distress. Recognising and integrating these aspects can promote mental well-being. When an individual is being praised what happens to her mentally? There will be an instant motivation and arousal of the ego, the inner child suddenly comes alive. Such may begin to perceive his shadow and make adjustments. Consequently, from the collective unconscious, the personal unconscious is being nudged.

x. Relationship with Personal Unconscious

While the personal unconscious is shaped by individual experiences, the collective unconscious is considered deeper and more fundamental. Jung believed that much of personal psychological distress stems from conflicts between the personal unconscious and the broader, archetypal forces within the collective unconscious (Roesler, 2023). The relationship with the personal unconscious is an on-going interplay between your conscious mind and the deeper, often hidden parts of your psyche. This concept, rooted in Carl Jung's analytical psychology, emphasises the personal unconscious as a reservoir of memories, experiences, emotions, and desires that influence your thoughts, behaviours, and decisions, often without your explicit awareness.

Connecting *Oríkì* and the Collective Unconscious

While *Oríkì* is specific to the Yoruba culture and Jung's Collective Unconscious is a universal psychological concept, both engage deeply with identity, memory, and shared human experience, offering potential parallels and intersections. In this same vein, *Oríkì* can be seen as reflecting specific cultural archetypes (memories) within the Yoruba collective consciousness. The themes, symbols, and figures praised in *Oríkì*, echo the archetypes Jung describes, but in a form tailored to Yoruba cosmology and social structure (Barber, 1991; Jung, 1968). As important to this concept is the notion of identity and heritage, both of which emphasise the importance of individuality and lineage. While *Oríkì* connects individuals to their specific cultural and familial lineage, Jung's Collective Unconscious connects individuals to a broader, shared human heritage through universal symbols and stories (Jung, 1936; Akinyemi, 2003). Transmission of Knowledge is another connection between the Jungian school and *Oríkì*. While *Oríkì* serves as a means of transmitting cultural knowledge, much like how Jung believed archetypes transmit universal patterns of experience through the collective unconscious which is a shared reservoir of unconscious psychological material that connects all humans. He theorised that these archetypes are innate, universal, and inherited patterns of thought and behaviour that shape human experiences, emotions, and actions (Vedor, 2023; McDonald, 2020).

Invocation of the Vigour of the Head and the Child in Jungian Tradition

In Jungian psychology, the "vigour of the head and the child" evokes themes of intellectual clarity and creative renewal, symbolically represented through archetypes and their interplay within the psyche. The "head" symbolises intellect, rationality, and conscious thought processes. It is associated with:

- a) **Logos Energy:** The archetypal masculine principle, representing logic, structure, and decision-making (Bowles, 1991).
- b) **The Wise Old Man/Woman:** This archetype embodies wisdom, guidance, and the distilled knowledge of life's experiences (Peterson, 2024).
- c) **Consciousness:** The "head" is the locus of ego-awareness and the capacity for reflection, crucial for navigating the world through reason and foresight (Wilberg, 2006; Hunt, 2008). From experience and data collected whenever the *Oríki* is being chanted, the chanted experiences a form of euphoria which they described as "head swelling" ((Rafiu & Adeyemi, 2013; Field survey, 2024). To them, it like their heads was invoked for productivity. They feel light, strong, motivated and ready for work.

The "child" in Jungian tradition is a powerful symbol of renewal, potential, and transformation (McGurn, 1998). It represents:

- a) **The Divine Child:** A motif found in mythology and religion symbolizing purity, hope, and the promise of new beginnings. This archetype often appears during phases of personal growth or individuation (Jung, 1996).
- b) **The Puer Aeternus (Eternal Youth):** A shadow form of the child archetype, representing the inability to grow or assume responsibility, but also signifying a longing for freedom and boundless creativity (Schwartz, 2024).
- c) **Rebirth:** The child often signifies the re-emergence of forgotten or neglected aspects of the self, hinting at the psyche's potential for renewal and integration (Hartman & Zimberoff, 2005).

In Jungian thought, the "head" and the "child" can be seen as complementary forces:

- a) **Integration of Rational and Creative Energies:** The "head" provides the clarity and structure necessary for the "child" to express creativity and explore possibilities.

- b) **Individuation:** The individuation process involves uniting conscious reasoning (head) with the unconscious, playful, and regenerative energies of the child.
- c) **Balancing Opposites:** The vigour of the head can sometimes suppresses the spontaneity of the child, and vice versa. Healthy psychological development requires balancing these energies. This point coincides with the Yoruba adage: *Orí inú kó má ba t'òde jẹ́*.

In essence, invoking the vigour of the head and the child within Jungian tradition encourages a holistic embrace of logic, wisdom, and creative renewal, fostering psychological growth and harmony.

Oríkì and AI: Connecting the Dots

The potential connection between *Oríkì* (also known as cognomentisation, a traditional Yoruba form of praise poetry) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) lies in the intersection of culture, linguistics, and technology. Here are several avenues where this connection might be explored:

i. Preservation and Documentation of Cultural Heritage

Digitisation of *Oríkì*: AI can be used as a method to digitise, preserve, and document *Oríkì*, which are often passed down orally from one generation to another (Devincenzi, 2023). By creating databases of these poems, AI can help in the transcription, translation, and annotation of *Oríkì*, making them accessible to future generations (Hautemo & Mushaandja, 2024). This can also include Text-to-Speech (TTS) and Speech Recognition. Hence, making AI models, particularly those in Natural Language Processing (NLP), can be trained to recognise and reproduce the tonal variations and rhythmic patterns of *Oríkì*, maintaining the integrity of the oral tradition in digital formats (Dai, 2023; Swargiary 2024).

ii. Linguistic Analysis and Evolution

Language Modelling is an evolution of the AI which can be used to study the structure, syntax, and semantics of the Yoruba language as reflected in *Oríkì* (Tijani, Akinwale, Onashoga & Adeleke, 2021). This can help linguists understand how the language has evolved over the years and how different regions have influenced the tradition (Ninan, Ajíbádé & Odéjobí, 2016). This action is also inflected in machine translation in

which AI-driven translation tools can be enhanced to better handle the nuances of Yoruba, particularly in translating *Oríkì* into other languages while maintaining the cultural context and poetic style (Bedu, & Bedu, 2024).

iii. Cultural AI Systems

Oríkì Generation: AI could potentially generate new *Oríkì* based on existing patterns and themes, either as a creative exercise or as a way to keep the tradition alive in modern contexts. This creativity is crafted engaging such elements as: a) Name of the individual (or family/clan name) which is the central theme of the *Oríkì*. b) Attributes/Qualities, which are personality traits, virtues, or accomplishments the owner wants to highlight; c) Lineage/Ancestry: Details of the family, hometown, or significant historical or cultural ties; d) Symbolic Connections: Natural elements, animals, or metaphor. The process of getting this done is through Personalised AI systems. These could be developed to create personalised *Oríkì* for individuals, drawing on the person's history, achievements, and lineage, similar to how traditional *Oríkì* are personalised to individuals or families. An example of personal AI generated oriki is one below with minimum customisation. This version provided below could be better and richer if I decide to infuse more attributes, symbolic elements, hometown, etc.

Òkélàná, ọmọ adé nílé nílé Ayé,

(Okelana, children of royalty, crowned upon the earth)

Èni tí ó mọ àwájọ kì í ònà,

(Those who walk with the wisdom of the elders never lose their way)

Èyin aláduúrà tó n gbẹ̀ kẹ̀ lé Ọlọ́run,

(You, the prayerful ones who trust in the Almighty)

Àwọ̀n tó n gbà gbé èrò ilé ayé,

(The ones who carry the weight of destiny with grace)

Òkélàná, ọmọ iràwọ̀ kì í sùn mọ́ lẹ̀,

(Okelana, descendants of the star that never falls)

Ọmọ alágbára tó ń fì ọgbọ́ n gba ogun,
(Children of might, who conquer battles with wisdom)

Ẹni tí ọ̀gì inú ọ̀gbó ń bọ́ ọ̀wọ́ ọ̀bì,
(Those whom the trees of the forest shield from harm)

Ọ̀kélà̀nà, ọ̀mọ ọ̀nı̀mọ́ tó ń gbé ọ̀ran wọ̀n sókè,
(Okelana, the knowledgeable ones who uplift their lineage)

Ẹyin akínkanjú tó fì ọ̀lá ẹ̀ ọ̀rẹ́,
(You, the brave ones who make honor their companion)

Omo ilẹ̀ tí ó ń dà bí ọ̀gìrì ńlá,
(Children of the land who stand firm like a great wall)

Ọ̀kélà̀nà, ẹ̀yin ọ̀kàn ọ̀kè tó ń dáké b̀ukátà,
(Okelana, hearts as strong as mountains, solving needs in silence)

iv. Interactive Educational Tools

Learning Yoruba Through *Oríkì* would require the use of AI-powered educational platforms as a tool for teaching the Yoruba language, offering interactive experiences where users can learn to compose or recite *Oríkì*. This could further enhance the possibilities of Cultural Exchange and Understanding among institutions. AI can help facilitate cross-cultural understanding by providing contextual explanations and interpretations of *Oríkì*, allowing people from different backgrounds to appreciate the depth and significance of this tradition (Chan, Banire, Ataguba, Frempong, & Orji, 2024).

v. Ethical and Philosophical Considerations

The use of AI requires some amount of cultural sensitivity in such a deeply cultural and personal tradition as *Oríkì*. This understanding raises questions about the ethical implications of automating or digitising human creativity and oral traditions (Sebbane, 2024). This thought is directly linked to reality of Intellectual Property. It is worth considering this in the contracting, ownership and the utilisation of generated *Oríkì*. Issues of ownership and intellectual property might

arise, especially regarding who "owns" an AI-generated *Oríkì* or who owns the rights to digitised and translated versions of traditional poems into other languages.

vi. AI as a Modern Griot

Storytelling and Historical Archives is the functionality of the AI which could function as a modern-day griot (traditional African storyteller), using databases of *Oríkì* and other oral histories to tell stories, preserve history, and promote cultural heritage in new engaging ways (Nordin, Almeida, & Wiberg, 2023; Trichopoulos, Alexandridis, & Caridakis, 2023). The concept of AI as a modern griot draws fascinating parallels between the traditional role of griots in African societies and the evolving capabilities of artificial intelligence (Repinecz, 2013; Monroe, S. (2021). By bridging *Oríkì* and AI, there's potential to innovate within the cultural space while maintaining respect for and understanding of the traditions that have shaped Yoruba culture for centuries.

Connotation of *Oríkì*

a. *Oríkì*: a Cognitive Process

In answering to memory and identity, *Oríkì* functions as a cognitive tool for recalling and reinforcing individual and shared identity. Through the recitation of *Oríkì*, individuals are reminded of their ancestry, accomplishments, awards and personal qualities. This process of recollection and reinforcement creates everyone's self-perception and social function in the context of their community (Barber, 2020). A good case is that of Soyinka whose memory of Ogun as his ancestry patron-god energises him to exhibit various positive attributes in the Nigerian society especially knowing that by reviving and controlling the people's collective will, Ogun was able to completely change the society (Ugochukwu, 2007). Viewing *Oríkì* as cognitive cultural creativity highlights the profound ways in which this tradition intertwines language, thought, culture, and artistry (Hallam & Ingold, 2021). It is not merely a form of praise or poetry, but a dynamic process that reflects and shapes cognitive and cultural realities. Through *Oríkì*, the Yoruba people engage in an on-going act of cultural creativity, continually redefining and reaffirming their identity and worldview. Using the instrumentation of metaphor, allusion, and symbolism in oral traditions such as *Oríkì* throws back the complex cognitive processes involved in Yoruba language and thought (Akinyemi & Falola, 2021). This further shows

how language creates and re-creates perception, facilitating multifaceted ideas to be transmitted and comprehended within a cultural context. Because the Yorùbá people utilise *Oríkì* for a variety of functions, it takes on diverse shapes. *Oríkì orílẹ̀* is a type of lineage poetry. This is employed to determine an individual's personality. Among other things, it is used to determine one's ancestry. When we consider *Oríkì* as "cognitive cultural creativity," we are exploring how this form of expression reflects the complex interplay between language, culture, cognition, and creativity.

b. *Oríkì*: Cultural Creativity

The strength of artistic expression cannot be overemphasised in *Oríkì* as an art form that requires creativity in composition and performance. The creation of *Oríkì* involves selecting and arranging words in a way that resonates culturally and emotionally with the audience. This creative process is influenced by cultural norms, but it also allows for individual expression and innovation. In addition to this is the strength of cultural transmission which comes with artistic expressions. As an oral tradition, *Oríkì* plays a crucial role in the transmission of cultural knowledge and values. Each recitation of *Oríkì* is an act of cultural creativity, as it not only preserves tradition but also adapts it to contemporary contexts and needs. This dynamic aspect ensures that *Oríkì* remains relevant across generations.

c. *Oríkì*: Social Contexts

Social Relationships are generated through *Oríkì* which often reinforces social bonds, celebrate achievements, or even critique behaviour (de Rhett, 2020; Foley, 2011). In this way, it functions as a cognitive tool for maintaining social order and cohesion. The creativity in *Oríkì* lies in its ability to navigate and articulate social relationships in a way that is culturally resonant. This includes the use of ritual and performance (Harms, 1979). This performance of *Oríkì* is not just a recitation but a deeply cultural act that often involves music, dance, and other forms of artistic expression. This performance aspect is another layer of cultural creativity, where the cognitive and emotional impact of *Oríkì* is heightened through multisensory experiences.

d. *Oríkì*: Philosophical Dimensions

The Yoruba philosophical dimensions of *Oríkì* can be diverse and defined according to the functionality of the entity. Firstly, *Oríkì* can be seen as a repository of Yoruba epistemology (Akinyemi & Falola, 2021).

In the delivery of *Oríkì*, knowledge of generational foundation is constructed, transmitted, and validated. *Oríkì* encapsulates an individual's lineage, personal achievements, and community's collective memory. It is a poetic articulation of who you are and where you come from. This aligns with the Yoruba philosophical concept of *Ori* (inner essence or destiny), emphasising self-awareness and purpose. Through *Oríkì*, individuals are reminded of their inherited virtues and responsibilities, fostering a sense of pride and accountability (Olúponà, J. K. (2022). Yoruba philosophy holds that each person has a unique destiny chosen before birth, and *Oríkì* often reflects this (Balogun, 2007). The invocation of *Oríkì* can be seen as a call to align one's actions with their destined purpose. The praises and attributes embedded in *Oríkì* act as affirmations that inspire individuals to strive toward fulfilling their potential. In the metaphysical dimension, the recitation of *Oríkì* is also an invocation of being (Kumari, 2022). It can be seen as an ontological act, where the spoken word has the power to shape reality, influencing the way individuals and communities understand themselves and their place in the world. The philosophical dimension of *Oríkì* lies in its profound representation of identity, destiny, and community in Yoruba culture. *Oríkì*, often described as praise poetry or an appellation, transcends mere words of adulation. It serves as a philosophical framework that reflects an individual's essence, heritage, and interconnectedness within the larger social and metaphysical order.

e. *Oríkì*: Functionalities

Oríkì can be given to a person at birth and often includes references to ancestors, lineage, achievements, and the characteristics that define them and the extended family. It is both a form of verbal art and a medium for preserving and transmitting cultural heritage (Olatunji, 1984). By default *Oríkì* depicts **personal identity** encapsulating the essence of an individual, connecting them to their ancestry and community. It is a way of affirming identity, values, and social roles (Barber, 1991). More so, it creates phenomenon of **Cultural Memory** which is the practice that preserves oral history and ensures that cultural knowledge and heritage are passed down through generations (Akinyemi, 2003).

Conclusion

In conclusion, considering cognomentisation or *Oríkì* as a Jungian archetype and a typology of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Yoruba Creativity highlights the symbiotic interplay between ancient archetypes and cutting-edge technologies. By situating AI within the framework of Yoruba cultural paradigms and Jungian typology, this exploration reveals the profound capacity for indigenous knowledge systems to inform and reshape our understanding of modern innovations. This synthesis underscores the adaptability of Yoruba creativity, offering a dynamic lens through which AI can be contextualised, personalised, and culturally enriched. Ultimately, this dialogue between tradition and technology not only deepens our grasp of AI's potential but also affirms the enduring relevance of cultural heritage in the evolving narrative of human ingenuity both in crafting words as the griots would have done, or in customising words as the AI is expecting to be doing in the nearest future. This becomes of great essence as the world experiences the decline in the raising of griots that are repositories of *Oríkì* of numerous Yoruba clans as well as the west of Africa.

References

- Abimbola, W. (1976). *Ifá: An Exposition of Ifá Literary Corpus*. Oxford University Press.
- Adebayo, K. (2022). *Oríkì and Technology: Preserving Yoruba Oral Traditions in the Digital Age*. Ibadan University Press.
- Adeoye, A. (2023). *Ethics and AI: The Implications of Automating Yoruba Oríkì*. *African Studies Review*, 45(1), 67-82.
- Akinyemi, A. (2003). *Yoruba Oral Tradition in Islamic Nigeria: A History of Dandani Praise Poetry*. Routledge.
- Akinyemi, A., & Falola, T. (Eds.). (2021). *The Palgrave Handbook of African Oral Traditions and Folklore*. Springer International Publishing.
- Babalola, A. (1966). *The Content and Form of Yoruba Ijala*. Oxford University Press.
- Balogun, O. A. (2007). The concepts of Ori and human destiny in traditional Yoruba thought: A soft-deterministic interpretation. *Nordic Journal of African Studies*, 16(1).
- Bangura, A. K. (2015). Pragmatic Linguistic Analysis of Isola. In Toyin Falola and African Epistemologies (pp. 137-152). New York: Palgrave Macmillan, US.

- Barber, K. (2020). *I Could Speak Until Tomorrow: Oriki, Women & the Past in a Yoruba Town*. Edinburgh University Press.
- Bassil-Morozow, H. (2023). Archetypes in Film and Television Narratives. In *Encyclopedia of Heroism Studies* (pp. 1-5). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Bedu, A. M., & Bedu, A. M. (2024). Artificial intelligence (AI) challenges and opportunities in translation: An African experience. *Al-Noor Journal for Humanities*, 2(3).
- Bowles, M. L. (1991). The organization shadow. *Organization Studies*, 12(3), 387-404.
- Burnett, I. S. (Ed.). (2023). *Re-visioning the American Psyche: Jungian, Archetypal, and Mythological Reflections*. Taylor & Francis.
- Chan, G., Banire, B., Ataguba, G., Frempong, G., & Orji, R. (2024). A Panoramic View of Socio-Cultural Sensitivity in Digital Technologies: A Comprehensive Review and Future Directions. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, 1-29.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2024.2372135>
- Cooper, C. (2020). *Gendered Confrontations with the Unconscious: Anima Animus and the Surrealist Woman*. Pacifica Graduate Institute.
- Dai, S. (2023). *Towards Artificial Musicians: Modeling Style for Music Composition, Performance, and Synthesis via Machine Learning* (Doctoral dissertation, Stanford University).
- de Rhett, B. M. (2020). The Structure and Changing Functions of Oral Traditions. In *Hispanic Balladry Today* (pp. 247-268). Routledge.
- Devincenzi, G. (2023). Father Figures: Renegotiating Preservation of Oral Tradition Through Four Forefathers. *The Serials Librarian*, 84(1-4), 17-21.
- Folayan, M. (2023). *Cultural AI: Bridging Tradition and Innovation in Yoruba Orature*. Lagos Publishing House.
- Foley, J. M. (2011). Oral tradition and its implications. In *A new companion to Homer* (pp. 146-173). Brill.
- Galli Carminati, G., Carminati, F., & Demongeot, J. (2024). A Gender-related Interpretation of Human Reproductive Behavior. *Int J Psychiatr Res*, 7(5), 1-20.
- Gorban, P. (2013). *Welcoming the shadow: Intimacy in depth invites wholeness*. Pacifica Graduate Institute.
- Gordon, S. (2023). Self-Actualization. In *The Mind-Brain Continuum: Psychoneurointracrinology* (pp. 73-93). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Hallam, E., & Ingold, T. (Eds.). (2021). *Creativity and cultural improvisation*. Routledge.

- Harms, R. (1979). Oral tradition and ethnicity. *The Journal of Interdisciplinary History*, 10(1), 61-85.
- Hartman, D., & Zimberoff, D. (2005). Trauma, transitions, and thriving. *Journal of Heart-Centered Therapies*, 8(1).
- Hauke, C. (2012). The unconscious: Personal and collective. In *The handbook of Jungian psychology* (pp. 54-73). Routledge.
- Hautemo, A. M., & Mushaandja, T. (2024, May). The Intersection between African Oral Literature and Technology. In *2024 IST-Africa Conference (IST-Africa)* (pp. 1-9). IEEE.
- Hill, G. (1998). Men, the anima, and the feminine. *The San Francisco Jung Institute Library Journal*, 17(3), 49-62.
- Hill, G. S. (2001). *Masculine and feminine: The natural flow of opposites in the psyche*. Shambhala Publications.
- Hunt, J. V. (2008). *A phenomenological study of the dream-ego in Jungian practice*, Doctoral dissertation, School of Psychology, University of Western Sydney
- Jung, C. G. (1936). *The Concept of the Collective Unconscious*. *Collected Works*, Vol. 9. Princeton University Press.
- Jung, C. G. (1959). *The Archetypes and The Collective Unconscious*. *Collected Works*, Vol. 9 (Part 1). Princeton University Press.
- Jung, C. G. (1968). *Man and His Symbols*. Doubleday.
- Jung, C. G. (1969). *The Archetypes and the Collective Unconscious*. Princeton University Press.
- Jung, C. G. (1996). *The psychology of the child archetype*. *Theories of myth; 1: Psychology and myth*, 215-245.
- Jung, C. G. (2014). *The archetypes and the collective unconscious*. Routledge.
- Jung, C. G., & von Franz, M.L. (1964). *Man and His Symbols*. Aldus Books.
- Knox, J. M. (2001). Memories, fantasies, archetypes: an exploration of some connections between cognitive science and analytical psychology. *Journal of Analytical Psychology*, 46(4), 613-635.
- Kumari, C. D. A. (2022). *Hand of Ifa: A Support Guide for Onifa, Beginning Awo Ifa, and Isese Ifa Devotees in the Diaspora*. Ori Institute.
- Loftin, M. (2010). *Four phases of animus development: A model for transformation*. Pacifica Graduate Institute.
- McDonald, K. L. (2020). *Jungian Archetypes: A Step Towards Scientific Enquiry* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Huddersfield).
- McGurn, P. A. (1998). *The divine child archetype in Jungian psychological thought and practice*. Pacifica Graduate Institute.
- Meier, I. (2023). *Jung and the Jungians: The Jungian Perspective*. In *Underlying Assumptions in Psychoanalytic Schools* (pp. 270-279). Routledge.

- Merriam-Webster. (n.d.). Cognomen. In Merriam-Webster.com thesaurus. Retrieved August 29, 2024, from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/thesaurus/cognomen>
- Merriam-Webster.com Thesaurus, s.v. “cognomen,” accessed August 29, 2024, <https://www.merriam-webster.com/thesaurus/cognomen>.
- Monroe, S. (2021). Tradition, Purpose, and Technology. *Afrofuturism in Black Panther: Gender, Identity, and the Re-Making of Blackness*, 245.
- Ninan, O. D., Ajíbádé, G. O., & Odéjóbí, O. A. (2016). Appraisal of computational model for yorùbá folktale narrative. In 7th Workshop on Computational Models of Narrative (CMN 2016). Schloss-Dagstuhl-Leibniz Zentrum für Informatik.
- Nordin, H., Almeida, T., & Wiberg, M. (2023). Designing to restore the past: Storytelling for empowerment through a digital archive. *International Journal of Design*, 17(1), 91-104.
- Nuorluoto, T. (2021). Roman Female Cognomina: Studies in the nomenclature of Roman women (Doctoral dissertation, Department of Linguistics and Philology, Uppsala University)
- Ogunleye, T. (2021). *Language and AI: The Role of Artificial Intelligence in the Evolution of Yoruba Syntax*. *Journal of African Languages and Linguistics*, 38(2), 120-134.
- Olatunji, O. O. (1984). *Features of Yoruba Oral Poetry*. University Press Limited.
- Olúponà, J. K. (2022). The Code of Twins. *Gemini and the Sacred: Twins and Twinship in Religion and Mythology*, 71.
- Peterson, C. (2024). *The Shadow of a Figure of Light: The Archetype of the Alcoholic and the Journey to Enlightenment*. Chiron Publications.
- Rafiu, K. A., & Adeyemi, R. O. (2013). Aspects of language and cultural endangerment: Examples from Yoruba. *Creative Artist: A Journal of Theatre and Media Studies*, 7(1), 63-78.
- Repinecz, J. (2013). *Whose Hero? Reinventing Epic in French West African Literature* (Doctoral dissertation, UC Berkeley).
- Roesler, C. (2023). *Deconstructing archetype theory: A critical analysis of Jungian ideas*. Routledge.
- Schwartz, S. E. (2024). *A Jungian Exploration of the Puella Archetype: Girl Unfolding*. Taylor & Francis.
- Sebbane, H. (2024.) *The Digital Custody: Cultural Perspectives On AI Generated Literature And Cultural Heritage Preservation* (Doctoral Dissertation, Université Kasdi Merbah-Ouargla). <https://dspace.univ-ouargla.dz/jspui/handle/123456789/37063>
- Stevens, A. (2012). The archetypes. In *The handbook of Jungian psychology* (pp. 74-93). Routledge.

- Swargiary, K. (2024). Sacred Codes: Artificial Intelligence and the Creation of Religious Texts. ERA, US.
- Taofeek, O., & Oyeyemi, A. (2022). Oríki: A Modified Oral System of Myth and Realism. *Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu Journal of Folklore and Cultural Studies*, 1(1).
- Tijani, O. D., Akinwale, A. T., Onashoga, A., & Adeleke, E. O. (2021). An Improved Aggregated Method for Generation of Yoruba Language Stop Words (Doctoral dissertation, Department of Computer Science, College of Physical Sciences, Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta).
- Trichopoulos, G., Alexandridis, G., & Caridakis, G. (2023). A survey on computational and emergent digital storytelling. *Heritage*, 6(2), 1227-1263.
- Ugochukwu, F. (2007). P. Barrot (ed.), *Nollywood – le phénomène video au Nigeria*. Paris: L'Harmattan (pb €18 – 2 7475 7971 9). 2005, 175 pp. *Africa*, 77(2), 287–288. doi:10.3366/afr.2007.77.2.287
- Vajjala, S., Majumder, B., Gupta, A., & Surana, H. (2020). *Practical natural language processing: a comprehensive guide to building real-world NLP systems*. O'Reilly Media.
- Vedor, J. E. (2023). Revisiting Carl Jung's archetype theory a psychobiological approach. *Biosystems*, 234, 105059.
- Vidal, Tunji' (1969). "Oriki in Traditional Yoruba Music". *African Arts*. 3 (1): 56–59. doi:10.2307/3334460. JSTOR 3334460
- Wilberg, P. (2006). *The Awareness Principle*. Advaita and European phenomenology.
- Yadav, A., Patel, A., & Shah, M. (2021). A comprehensive review on resolving ambiguities in natural language processing. *AI Open*, 2, 85-92.
- Zgusta, L. (2024, November 7). Name. *Encyclopedia Britannica*. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/name>